

ISSN: 2456-5474

RNI No. UPBIL/2016/68367

VOL.- X , ISSUE- I February - 2025
Innovation The Research Concept

Mediating Role of Perceived Organizational Support in the Relationship between Employees' Perception of Violation of Norms of Justice and Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Paper Id : 19809 Submission Date : 2025-02-11 Acceptance Date : 2025-02-22 Publication Date : 2025-02-25
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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.14978678

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Hari Om Gupta

Associate Professor
Psychology Department
B.R.D. PG. College
Deoria, U.P., India

Abstract

Purpose: The present research work was done to study the mediating role of perceived organizational support in the relationship between employees' perception of violation of norms of justice and organizational citizenship behavior..

Design/Methodology/Approach: The study was done on 250 employees of Public and Private Organizations (125 from each). On the basis of an interview done on some of the employees from both the sectors i.e. Public and Private, a scale for measuring perceived violation of norms of justice was developed. For measuring other variables, standard scales were used. Data were collected through questionnaire method. For analysis, mediation analysis were done.

Findings: Results showed that perceived organizational support mediated the relationship between employees' perception of violation of norms of justice and organizational citizenship behaviour.

Practical Implications: The study has implications for scholars of organizational behavior, to look into the organizational problems from the perspective of employees i.e. what do the employees think of existing social norms.

Social Implications: This study shows that employees/humans are vital factors in the running/success of any organizations/society.

Originality: The research is original in the sense that it tries to compare employees' perception of Justice Norms in both Public and Private Organizations.

Keywords Perception of Violation of Norms of Justice, Perceived Organizational Support and Organizational Citizenship Behavior.

Introduction

An organization is a social unit of people that is structured and managed to meet a need or to pursue collective goals. All organizations have a management structure that determines the relationship between different activities and the members and sub divides and assign roles

Objective of study

To study the role of mediating variables i.e. perceived organizational support on the relationship between 'perceived violation of norms' and outcome variables i.e. organizational citizenship behaviour.

Review of Literature**Justice Concerns in Organizations**

We can understand why justice is important by remembering that fairness concerns itself with what things get allocated and how these allocations take place. Thus, to say that justice matters are more or less synonymous with maintaining that people care about how they are with others. The roots of justice can be found in our inclination to affiliate with other people. This is also well explained by Sampson (1975) "Just solution-promote cohesion and order, including a state of psychological well-being while unjust solutions contribute to personal and social unrest and disorganization." Thus, Justice is essential for psychological functioning and welfare of the individual.

Issues relating to fairness become more salient in the case of organizational work setting. Theorists have recognized justice as a key organizational value (Lind and Tyler, 1988) - "the morale problem for years to come will be one of justice. The modern survey to maximally useful will centre more on problems of fairness procedures of payment of promotion and so forth, than on conditions of work as the closeness of supervisions per se." People become no less animated by justice when they arrive at work. In fact, concerns over injustice have provided impetus to the labour movement (Fantasia, 1988). Presently, the language of justice is shaping dialogue concerning global capitalism in developing nations (Greider, 1997).

Moreover, also research conducted across a variety of contexts (e. g., layoffs, drug testing, and pay cuts) in both laboratory and field settings demonstrates the importance of treating employees in a fair manner(Konovsky,2000). Recent reviews and meta-analytic studies examining justice at the individual level indicate fairness is a correlate or predictor of a no. of important organizational outcomes. For example, perceptions of fairness have been positively associated with favorable employees attitudes and behaviours including organizational commitment, organizational support, OCBs, work performance, and trust in management(e. g., Cohen-Charash & Spector,2001; Colquitt, Conlon, Wesson, Porter, & Ng,2001;).However, when treated unfairly, employees are likely to react in unfavorable ways such as engaging in counterproductive work behaviours(e. g., damaging company property or spreading rumors), turnover, and theft(Cropanzano, Byrne, Bobocel, & Rupp,2001).

Thus, it is clear that justice matters and that people care about justice for a variety of reasons (i.e., people may even defend the view that justice is omnipresent and that the pursuit of justice is in itself a guiding and moral directive in our social lives.

Main Text**Different Norms of Justice**

At most general level, organizational justice is an area of psychological inquiry that focuses on perceptions of fairness in the workplace. Instances of justice take a variety of forms and researchers have throughout the last few decades devoted much attention to distinguishing among different "types" of justice (e.g., Bies & Moag, 1986; Greenberg & Colquitt, 2005; Thiabou & Walker, 1975). More precisely, justice involves issues of distribution, treatment, formal and informal decision-making procedures, and so forth. So it can be said that individuals' perceptions of fairness in organizational settings have been conceptualized regarding at least three separate types of organizational justice. The first category centered on:

Distributive Justice: It is a kind of justice in which fairness was defined regarding the outcomes of a resource allocation decision. Three rules have been identified as the basis people use for distributive justice i.e. equity, equality and need.

Procedural Justice: In the organizational context, procedural justice is considered a valuable resource in social exchange. Procedural justice is an appraisal of the process by which an allocation decision is (or was) made. Evidence now shows that when people believe that decision-making processes are unjust, they show less commitment to their employers, more theft, higher turnover intentions, lower performance, and fewer cooperative citizenship behaviors (for recent reviews, see Cropanzano & Greenberg, 1997).

Interactional Justice: The literature on employee-employer relations shows that an employee expects the organization to treat him/her with respect, dignity, honesty and to extend equal treatment to all members (Janssens, Sels, & Van den Brande, 2003; Kickul & Liao Troth, 2003). Bies & Moag (1986) referred to this notion as interactional justice, which is the perception of the quality of treatment an employee receives when

policies and procedures are implemented in the workplace. Perceptions of interactional justice play a role in the determination of employees' attitudes and behaviour (Cohen-Charash & Spector, 2001; Colquitt, Conlon, Wesson, Porter, & Yee Ng, 2001).

As the literature reviews show that a no. of researches have done relating different types of justice to the different type of outcomes, but meager studies is indicating the relationship of overall justice to organizational outcomes.

Responses to Violation of Norms of Justice:

Overall, the result of studies done, suggests that organizational justice may be predictive of different attitudes and behaviours (Greenberg, 1990). The different reactions are like outcome satisfaction, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, trust, agent-referenced evaluations, withdrawal organizational citizenship behaviour, adverse reactions and much more like that.

The present research undertakes to study how organizational level outcome variables such as and Perceived Organizational Support get influenced when there is the perception of violation of norms in the organizations. The reason for taking these variables lies in their importance to organizations as a whole because if the employees in the organization do not feel perceived organizational support. then, it will adversely affect the both growth and production of the organizations. Moreover, the issues become more salient in the context of Public and Private Organizations.

Organizational Citizenship Behaviour(OCB): Katz and Kahn (1966) defined it as sup-role behaviours that improved the effectiveness of the organization. In the words of Katz and Kahn(1966) this, "includes any gestures that lubricate the social machinery of the organization and do not directly adhere to the usual notion of task performance". The extra-role behaviours identified included helping other workers with work-related problems, accepting others into the work group without a fuss, either putting up with or minimizing interpersonal conflict in the organization, and protecting and conserving organizational resources. Katz and Kahn (1966) coined the term "citizenship" to represent the workers that displayed these extra-role behaviours.

Citizenship behaviour is employee behaviour that is above and beyond the call of duty and is therefore discretionary and not rewarded in the context of an organization's formal reward structure. It is work behaviour that holds promise for long term organizational effectiveness and success. This behaviour is also referred to as prosocial organizational behaviour (Brief & Motowidlo, 1986), extra-role behaviour (Van Dyne & Cummings, 1990), organizational spontaneity (George & Brief, 1992), and even counter role behaviour (Staw & Boettger, 1990). Organ (1994) referred to a person who engages in OCB as a "good soldier".

Thus, on the basis of studies done on organizational commitment and Organizational Citizenship Behaviour(OCB) , it can be infer that it is an important organizational levelvariable influenced by a no. of factors like perceived organizational support and job satisfaction, employee level variables.

Organizational commitment is associated with many important work attitudes and behaviours, such as job satisfaction and work performance (Meyer, Paunonen, Gellatly, Goffin & Jackson, 1989; Mowday et.al., 1982).

Perceived Organizational Support (POS): Eisenberger, Huntington, Hutchison, and Sowa (1986) proposed that employees form global beliefs about the extent to which an organization values their contributions and cares about their well being. They called this set of beliefs Perceived Organizational Support (POS). In other words, POS can be viewed as an employee belief that the organization cares for and values his or her contribution to the success of organization (Kaufman et al., 2001).Eisenberger, Fasolo, and Davis-La Mastro (1990) suggested that employees would consider positive discretionary activities by the organization that benefited them as evidence that the organization cared about their well being.

It appears then that, as suggested by Eisenberger and colleagues (1990), POS may be vital for determining if any attitudes or behaviors benefiting the organization, like affective commitment or citizenship behaviors, emerge from the employment relationship.

Current research shows that perceived organizational support (POS) influences some important employee attitudes and behaviours such as organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB), organizational commitment (OC)

Hypothesis Perceived Organizational Support will mediate the relationship between perception of violation of norms of justice by the employees in the organization and organizational citizenship behaviour.

Methodology Sample: The present study will be based on a sample of 250 employees. The sample will include employees from both sectors i.e. public and private. Data will be collected through questionnaire method.

Development of scale for measuring Perception of Justice: To develop a scale for measuring perception of justice in the organization by the employees, pilot interviews were conducted on the employees. The total numbers of employees were 20, out of

which 12 were of private, and eight were from the public. By answers given to some issues, items were formed. Finally, following no. of the articles was taken from administration:

Distributive Justice: 26

Procedural Justice: 19

Interactional Justice: 18

Organizational Citizenship Behaviour: will be measured with the scale developed by Bettercourt et.al,(2000) The scale has 16 items.

Perceived Organizational Support: will be measured with the scale developed by Eisenberger et,al, (1986). The scale consists of 17 items.

Result and Discussion

Table: 1 Mediation analysis for Perceived Organizational Support: Predicting Organizational Citizenship Behaviour with Perception of Violation of Norms of Justice (N=250).

Predictors	F	Beta(β)	t
Perception of Violation of Norms of Justice	Mediator Variable: Perceived Organizational Support		
	654.63	-0.85	-25.58**
Perception of Violation of Norms of Justice	Dependent Variable: Organizational Citizenship Behaviour		
	928.97	-0.88	-30.47**
PVN, Perceived Organizational Support	Dependent Variable: Organizational Citizenship Behaviour		
	544.10	PVN= -0.56 POS=-0.37	-11.30** -7.44**

Note*p<0.05; **p<0.01; PVN= Perception of Violation of Norms of Justice, POS=Perceived Organizational Support

Justice is important to our social as well as organizational functioning as is explained by the fact that the concept of justice (as well as its violation) often dictates our daily experiences and discussions (e. g., Finkel, 2001; Folger, 1984).This research has been done with the purpose of understanding how does the perceived organizational support mediate the relationship between perception of violation of norms of justice in the organizations by the employees and personal level outcome variables organizational citizenship behaviour.

In general, the results supported most of the developed hypothesized relationship. Since in our study, the focus was to study employees" perception of violation of norms of justice, so the two organizations were taken. Of the two agencies, one was from public sector while other was from the private sector. Results supported that private organization employees will perceive less violation of norms of justice in comparison to the public organization employees. Studies conducted in an organizational context, taking Public/Private sector as antecedent factors have found that these organizations differ regarding climate and norms. (Roy, 1974; de, 1974; Prasad, 1979; Sinha, 1973); organizational activities and reinforcement patterns, control of economy, autonomy, layers of management, communication network, etc. These differences generated a complicated system of feelings, expectations, perceptions, attitudes and values in their employees which in turn influences outcome variables organizational citizenship behaviour.

Result (Table No.1) showed that perceived organizational support mediated the relationship perceived violation of norms of justice and outcome variable organizational citizenship behaviour. The explanation for this finding might be that when employees feel that he/she are not getting fair amount of treatment in terms of distribution of resources, implementation of rules and respect from the co-workers and organization than their perceived organizational support which is responsive to immediate situations in the organization, get diminished. And this reduction in perceived organizational support decreases their involvement in organizational citizenship behaviour. The result section also supports the findings in which it was shown that perceived violation of norms of justice significantly related with perceived

organizational support which in turn significantly related with organizational citizenship behaviour.

Conclusion

Results showed that perceived organizational support mediated the relationship between employees' perception of violation of norms of justice and organizational citizenship behaviour.

Practical Implications: The study has implications for scholars of organizational behavior, to look into the organizational problems from the perspective of employees i.e. what do the employees think of existing social norms.

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